

A review paper on Design And Performance Evaluation Of Drowning Death Prevention System With various technologies.

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1. Abstract:

Drowning is most terrifying accident to most of the children and adult which prevent them from using swimming pools for recreation and fitness .The present article focuses on accuracy in drown predict ,notify and saving inventions .Comparison and short falls in research work done so far done .Research gaps were identified in available art work and proposed improvements .This review article focused mainly of drown safety related inventions and research articles in databases .The present study thrown light on how many technologies were being used to predict and avoid drown deaths .

Key words – IoT, Hydrophones ,blood-oxytometry ,swimming-pools , drown ,safety ,image processing ,thermal cameras , automatic-rescue ,embedded .

2. INTRODUCTION

As per the world health organization, drowning is the major cause of unintentional deaths across the deaths of healthy people while doing swimming in swimming pools. Several techniques are suggested by several research articles and patents.The present research is to study and suggest an improved method to save drowning victims. The present attempt try to suggest innovative robust methods to detect, alarm and make automatic attempts to save a drowning person. The present study may bring novel methods to avoid the fear of death in swimming pools both domestic as well as a public pool.

Drowning is a silent phenomenon where the victim will never show significant signs before or near-drowning incidents and silently lose a life. Since swimming is a healthy sport for cardiovascular and good for overall body fitness, and stress relieving exercise, everybody loves to use swimming pools. But a good amount of care is must to maintain these pools otherwise these pools will cause unintentional deaths to kids and elderly people.

3. Review of Literature

The following is a brief description of the work published by researchers on drowning prevent and avoid devices.